

Effect of Backpack on the Spinal Health of Lower-Level High School Students in Nigeria using Taguchi

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ABSTRACT:

Poor posture has become a big problem globally, especially among young scholars within formative ages. This disorder is not uncommon where the spine has been unnecessarily loaded. Therefore, this work was centred on examining the effect of backpacks on spine health of lower-level high school students, selected across a lower-level secondary school in Ibadan, Nigeria. Their spines, loaded with backpacks, were checked on arrival in school (SPLM), and after closing (SPLA) using a flexicurve. Their heights and weights were also determined simultaneously, using a stadiometer and digital weighing balance. Data were analysed using descriptive statistics and Taguchi method. 96 subjects altogether participated. Descriptive statistics showed mean age, median, mode; mean subjects weight, median weight; average bag weight, median, mode; mean SPLM, mean SPLA; mean morning height, and mean afternoon height to be (12.75,13,13; 36.74kg, 35.50kg; 4.64kg, 4.00kg, 5.00kg; 14.35,14.86; 151.59cm and 152.47cm) respectively. Taguchi approach showed that bag weight (delta = 2.53), was the primary factor influencing the spinal length of the subjects. Moreover, in terms of their backpack weights, 59.40% of the subjects fall within medium category, meaning that most of them may be at risk for moderate spinal strain. In conclusion, significant relationships exist between backpack weight and self-reported shoulder and backpain, In addition, bag weight significantly influences spinal length, with heavier backpacks associated with greater reductions. It is thus recommended that ergonomic measures be fully implemented in order to mitigate the risk of bad posture due to backpack weights.

Keywords: Backpack, spine, posture, descriptive statistics, ergonomics.

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INTRODUCTION

Bad posture has become a terrible menace in many societies across the globe [1]. Findings have shown that 40 – 70% of school children, aging between 7 and 10 years in developed countries suffer bad posture, due to prolonged spinal loading, with the underlying pain referred to as back pain syndrome [1]. Usually, a child with backpack leans forward, trying to balance centre of gravity, and leading to lumbar lordosis decrease, with increase in thoracic kyphosis [1]. Some school children carry as much as 30 – 40% of their entire body weight as backpacks [2]. Unfortunately, school children in this category still have their musculoskeletal systems undergoing several developments. These excessive loads are believed to cause increased forward lean, pain and skin pressure in concerned school children [2].

Carrying backpacks have also been found to affect plantar pressure distribution and gait parameters in children [3]. Brisk walking or running while carrying a backpack leads to an increase in vertical reaction force, which in turn increases the risk of lower extremity injuries [4]. Ideally, keeping of books and school-related materials in schools lockers would have solved the problem of excessive backpack loading, but fear of vandalism often discourage students from keeping valuable items in school lockers. Factors which constantly contribute to increased backpack loading include: increased homework, laptops, palmtops, musical instruments, drawing instruments, and sporting equipment [2]. An injury, identified as rucksack palsy, common among backpack carrying occupations (8 – 45kg) has also been discovered amongst some backpack-carrying school children [2]. Although adults involved in such professions may have mastered how to balance such loads, young school students do not have this ability yet, in addition to their rapidly developing body parts at that tender age, which may lead to deformed or injured spine [5].

Backpack is one of the many forms of manually carrying loads, which gives room for versatility, and commonly utilised by school students and military personnels among others [5]. Lower back pain occurs in people with flatter spines, instead of S-shape, across all ages, but deteriorates as age advances [6]. It has been reported that of the entire world population, not less than 1.2 billion are adolescents [7]. This stage is very important, as both tissue and skeletal growth occur therein, and where care is not taken, musculoskeletal disorders set in [7]. A recent research, conducted on prevalence of bad spinal health in 134 children revealed scoliosis in 21% and kyphosis in 7.5% of the children [8]. It was also found that 42% of the children incorrectly carried their backpacks on one shoulder. Backpack loads in elementary and middle school children are vital, as these become risk factor for back pain occurrence, which often prolong into their adulthood [9]. Although originally designed to bring relief and comfort to students, backpacks are becoming sources of serious postural deviations and musculoskeletal disorders in children and teenagers when not loaded with caution [9], [10].

Furthermore, it has been reported that carrying a backpack with higher load than the carrying capacity of the muscle groups can lead to overhead, spine reflection, pain, structural changes or dysfunction [9][11]. It is a common trend to see young scholars with backpacks in different parts of the world [11]. Often times, depending on the age of the young students, weights of most backpacks are greater than 10 – 20% of the body weight of their carriers. Developed countries, such as Poland, England and Spain have recorded rampant cases of back pain in young scholars within the age range of 10 and 19, due to overweighed backpack or method of carriage [11]. However, in developing countries, risks of back pain reports are higher (about 3.5 times), as the young scholars not only carry, but still have to walk across long distances with their backpacks [11].

It thus becomes necessary to additionally appraise backpack designs, carriage method, load limit, alongside psychological, physiological and biomechanical responses to carrying of loads under different condition [11], [12]. It has also been found that back pain was common among adolescent secondary school students with activities requiring bending, carrying backpacks, and too much sitting [13]. However, the cross-sectional nature of the study dissuaded the drawing of cause-and-effect conclusions. Another research discovered a higher lifetime, annual and point prevalence of lower back pain among African nations compared to the reported global figures, with Nigeria and South Africa topping the list of the sample investigated [14]. As backpacks overweight often result to back

pain, musculoskeletal disorders and poor posture, it has been suggested that a symmetrical backpack with a load not exceeding 20%, or an asymmetrical single strap athletic bag with a load not exceeding 10% should be mandated for school children to promote their growth and safety [15]. Quite a number of investigations have been conducted in many countries across the world on backpacks and back pain, however, information on this in Nigeria remains sparse. Therefore, this work was centred on appraising the effect of backpacks on the spinal health of secondary school children in Oyo State, Nigeria, who are in their early adolescent ages. Hence, the objectives of this work include: 1) Visiting a selected secondary school for data collection. 2) Analysing collected data statistically. 3) Drawing inferences on the analysed data.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study setting

The study was conducted on high school students in Ibadan, Oyo state, South-western Nigeria.

Study Design

The study adopts a cross-sectional study design to investigate the effect of backpack use on the spinal health of secondary school students. The study incorporated Taguchi Design of Experiments (DOE) methodology to identify and analyse the influence of various factors on spinal length. Additionally, traditional statistical tests were used to quantify the effects and relationships of this impact.

Study Population

This study involved lower-level high school students in Ibadan, Oyo state, Nigeria.

Data Collection

Materials and devices for data collection

- I. Stadiometer: For height determination, in metres (m).
- II. Flexicurve: For spine length determination (C_7 to S_1). C_7 is the vertebra (bone) prominent at the base of the neck. S_1 is the vertebra close to the top of the sacrum, shortly above the tail bone.
- III. Digital weighing scale: For weight determination, in kilogramme (kg).
- IV. Measuring tape: For length determination, in centimetres (cm).
- V. Plain paper: For tracing the spine curve.
- VI. Pen and paper: For recording points and observations made, on interacting with the young adolescents (subjects).
- VII. Table and floor: As flat surfaces.

Procedures for data collection

I. Determination of some personal information

Focus was on young adolescents (subjects) from the junior high school category (J.S.1 to J.S.3). On arrival into the school premises, subjects who fall into this category were interacted with, and as such, information on their sex and age were noted and recorded. Furthermore, their individual weights and bag weights among others, were also checked using a digital weighing scale. These were captured twice a day (in the morning and afternoon, after the closing hour).

II. Determination of heights of the subjects

1. Using the floor as a flat surface, each subject was in turn asked to remove shoes and caps, and thereafter asked to stand upright, on the stadiometer (base), positioned on the floor, with heels positioned closely together, arms by the sides, back as straight as possible and knees not bending in any way.

2. Before reading the height of each of the subjects, it was ascertained that: back of the head, the shoulders and buttocks all touch the vertical board of the stadiometer, with the eyes positioned in a straight, not tilted manner.

3. Thereafter, the horizontal headpiece of the stadiometer was slowly brought down, and as such, it safely touched the top of the head of each subject in question.

4. Thereafter, the height was captured at the eye level to avoid parallax error, and recorded immediately. The procedures were repeated twice for every subject involved in the research (morning, on arrival in school, and afternoon, after closing time).

III. Determination of spine lengths of the subjects

1. A flexicurve was pressed along the spine of the subject, cutting across the C₇ and S₁. Care was taken to avoid stretching, so as to accurately trace out the natural curvature.

2. On tracing out the spine shape with the flexicurve, it was positioned on a piece of paper on a flat table, and afterwards traced out along the edge of the flexicurve with a pen.

3. Thereafter, using a measuring tape, the length along the curve was confirmed by marking out, and adding up small points along the flexicurve.

4. With the above steps, spine length was determined and recoded in centimetres for all the subjects, on arrival in the morning, and afternoon, after closing hour.

Precautions taken: Subjects were kept still during their measurements. Hard presses were avoided by all means. Sectionalising of the spine measurement in cases of tall subjects for accuracy.

Experimental Design Using Taguchi

The Taguchi method is particularly useful in optimizing processes by identifying significant factors with a reduced number of experimental runs. For this study, five key factors were selected: Age, Weight, Bag Weight, Shoulder Pain, and Back Pain. Each of these factors was evaluated at two levels, representing the minimum and maximum values observed in the dataset. The outcome variable of interest is the spinal length. An L12 orthogonal array design was chosen to structure the experiment, allowing for an efficient examination of the five factors across their two levels. The "Larger is better" criterion was selected for the Signal-to-Noise (S/N) ratio, as the goal was to maximize the outcome. The Taguchi DOE was carried out using Minitab software. The Signal-to-Noise (S/N) ratio for the "Larger is better" criterion was calculated using Equation (1)

$$SN_L = -10 \log \frac{1}{n} \left(\sum_{j=1}^n \frac{1}{y_j^2} \right) \quad (1)$$

Where n = number of observations, y_j = response variable.

Data Analysis

The data analysis was performed using IBM SPSS Statistics. The following statistical methods were employed to examine the effect of backpacks on the spinal health of secondary school students.

1. Frequency Distribution: This analysis was used to examine the prevalence of categorical variables such as Shoulder Pain, Back Pain, and Bag Weight Group as reported by the subjects. The process involved categorizing the data into specific groups or intervals to count the occurrences of each category. Using SPSS Statistics software, data for the selected variables were inputted, and the *Frequencies* function was applied to generate frequency tables. These tables outlined the

number and percentage of participants falling into each category. Also, bar charts and pie charts were generated to visually depict the distribution of these categorical variables.

2. Descriptive Statistics: Descriptive statistics were calculated to summarize the continuous variables in the dataset. Key descriptive measures such as mean, median, mode and standard deviation values were used to describe the central tendency and variability of these variables. The process involved importing the dataset into IBM SPSS Statistics software and selecting the *Descriptive Statistics* function. These metrics provided a comprehensive overview of the data distribution, enabling a clear understanding of the characteristics of the study population.

i. Paired T-Test:

Paired t-Test 1: SPLM vs. SPLA

- Null Hypothesis (H_0): There is no significant difference in spinal length measured in the morning (SPLM) and in the afternoon (SPLA).
- Alternative Hypothesis (H_1): There is a significant difference in spinal length measured in the morning (SPLM) and in the afternoon (SPLA).

Paired t-Test 2: Height M vs. Height A

- Null Hypothesis (H_0): There is no significant difference in height measured in the morning (Height M) and in the afternoon (Height A).
- Alternative Hypothesis (H_1): There is a significant difference in height measured in the morning (Height M) and in the afternoon (Height A).

ii. Chi-square test of Independence.

The Chi-Square Test of Independence was conducted to examine the association between various categorical variables in relation to the research objective of understanding the impact of backpack weight on spinal health. Specifically, the relationships between (i) Shoulder Pain and Back Pain, (ii) Shoulder Pain and Bag Weight Category, and (iii) Back Pain and Bag Weight Category were analysed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Following the procedures as described under sections 2.4 to 2.6, the following data (Table 1 - Appendix) and results were obtained.

As shown in Table 1, 96 subjects were involved in the study (aging between 9 and 15).

Factor Influence

The Taguchi analysis, as shown in Table 2, indicate that bag weight is the primary factor influencing spinal length among secondary school students. With a Delta value of 2.53, it ranks as the most significant factor, far exceeding the influence of others. This finding shows the critical impact of bag weight on spinal health, suggesting that heavier bags are strongly associated with greater reductions in spinal length.

Table 2. Response Table for Signal to Noise Ratios

Level	Age	Weight	Back Pain	Shoulder Pain	Bag Weight
1	23.68	23.40	23.52	23.82	22.06
2	23.24	23.48	23.37	23.13	24.59
Delta	0.44	0.08	0.15	0.68	2.53
Rank	3	5	4	2	1

Prevalence and Distribution of Key Factors

Figure 1 shows the gender distribution within the sample. The sample consisted of 96 subjects, with a slightly higher representation of males ($n = 52, 54.2\%$) compared to females ($n = 44, 45.8\%$). This nearly equal distribution ensures that both sexes are well-represented in the analysis, allowing for balanced comparisons and reducing potential gender bias in the study's findings.

Figure 1. Distribution of Gender

Figure 2 shows that majority of subjects reported no shoulder pain ($n = 80, 83.3\%$), while a smaller proportion reported experiencing shoulder pain ($n = 16, 16.7\%$). Similarly, most participants did not report back pain ($n = 90, 93.8\%$), with only a small number indicating that they experienced back pain ($n = 6, 6.3\%$). These findings imply that although back and shoulder pain is not common in the sample, a significant minority of students report such symptoms. With this research focused on how backpack weight affects spinal health, the comparatively lower rates of reported discomfort may suggest that the impacts of large backpacks on shoulder and back health are more subtle, or that they only show up in susceptible individuals.

Figure 2. Distribution of Shoulder Pain

Figure 3. Distribution of Backpain

The subjects were classified into three categories based on the weight of the bags they carried: Light (up to 3 kg), Medium (3-6 kg), and Heavy (above 6 kg). The frequency analysis in Figure 4 revealed that the majority of participants fell into the medium category (n = 57, 59.4%), indicating that most students carried a moderate load. The Light category accounted for 31.3% of the participants (n = 30), while the Heavy category, representing those carrying the heaviest loads, comprised 9.4% of the sample (n = 9). This result is noteworthy because it implies that most students may be at risk for moderate spinal strain as a result of the weight of their backpacks. The observed distribution supports the study's objective of assessing spinal health risks and may inform future recommendations for safe load limits in school settings.

Figure 4. Distribution of Bag Weight Group

Descriptive Analysis

Table 3 presents the descriptive statistics, the subjects in this study (N = 96) had a mean age of 12.75 years (SD = 1.23), with the majority being 13 years old, as indicated by the mode and median both being 13. This narrow age range reflects a relatively homogeneous group, consistent with the study's focus on school-aged children. The mean weight of the participants was 36.74 kg (SD = 8.01), with a median weight of 35.5 kg, showing that while the group is similar in age, there is greater

variability in body weight, likely due to natural differences in growth and development at this stage of adolescence.

The average bag weight carried by participants was 4.64 kg (SD = 4.56), with a median of 4.00 kg. The mode of 5.0 kg suggests that a significant number of students are carrying bags with weights that may pose a risk to spinal health, especially given their developing bodies. The mean spinal length measured in the morning (SPLM) was 14.35 cm (SD = 1.13), with a slight increase to 14.86 cm (SD = 1.25) in the afternoon (SPLA). Similarly, height measurements show a slight increase from morning to afternoon, with the mean height in the morning (Height M) being 151.59 cm (SD = 8.59) and in the afternoon (Height A) being 152.47 cm (SD = 9.07). However, the standard deviations suggest variability in the extent of this change, which may be influenced by factors such as the duration for which backpacks are carried.

Table 3. Descriptive Statistics

	Age	Weight	Bag Weight	SPLM	SPLA	Height M	Height A
Mean	12.75	36.738	4.640	14.353	14.857	151.591	152.471
Median	13.00	35.500	4.000	14.300	15.000	152.450	152.700
Mode	13	30.0	5.0	15.0	15.0	155.0	148.0
Std. Deviation	1.231	8.0103	4.5599	1.1329	1.2499	8.5855	9.0665

Paired T-Test

In Table 4, both paired t-tests indicate a statistically significant difference in spinal length and height from morning to afternoon, supporting the hypothesis that carrying backpacks have measurable impact on students' spinal health. This suggests that students' height and spinal length decrease when the measurement is taken in the morning and stretches out just before the reading is taken in the closing hour of the day. This decrease is attributed to the spinal compression caused by carrying heavy backpacks during the day. This result further strengthens the evidence that the daily use of backpacks has a measurable impact on students' spinal health, consistent with the objective of this study.

Table 4. Paired Samples Test

		T	df	Sig (2-tailed)
Pair 1	SPLM - SPLA	-5.873	95	0.000
Pair 2	HeightM – HeightA	-2.070	95	0.041

Chi-square Test of Independence

1. Association between Shoulder Pain and Backpain

Table 5 shows the cross-tabulation between the shoulder pain and back pain. The Pearson Chi-Square test (A) in Table 6 indicated that the association between shoulder pain and back pain was statistically significant, $\chi^2 (1, N = 96) = 32.00, p < .001$. This significant result suggests that students experiencing shoulder pain are more likely to also report back pain.

Table 5. Shoulder Pain and Backpain Cross Tabulation

			Backpain		Total
			No	Yes	
Shoulder Pain	No	Count	80	0	80
		Expected Count	75.0	5.0	80.0
	Yes	Count	10	6	16
		Expected Count	15.0	1.0	16.0
Total		Count	90	6	96
		Expected Count	90.0	6.0	96.0

Table 6. Chi-Square Test (A)

	Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	32.000	1	.000
Likelihood Ratio	23.718	1	.000

2. Association between Backpack Weight Group and Back Pain

Table 7 shows the cross-tabulation between the backpack weight group and back pain. The Pearson Chi-Square test (B) in Table 8 yielded a significant result, $\chi^2 (2, N = 96) = 41.58, p < .001$, indicating a statistically significant association between backpack weight and the presence of back pain. Specifically, students carrying heavier backpacks were significantly more likely to report back pain compared to those carrying lighter or medium-weight backpacks. These findings suggest that the weight of backpacks is a critical factor influencing the development of back pain among students.

Table 7. Bag Weight Group and Backpain Cross tabulation

			Backpain		Total
			No	Yes	
Bag Weight Group	Light	Count	29	1	30
		Expected Count	28.1	1.9	30.0
	Medium	Count	57	0	57
		Expected Count	53.4	3.6	57.0
	Heavy	Count	4	5	9
		Expected Count	8.4	.6	9.0
Total		Count	90	6	96
		Expected Count	90.0	6.0	96.0

Table 8. Chi-square Test (B)

	Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	41.576	2	.000
Likelihood Ratio	23.754	2	.000

3. Association between Backpack Weight Group and Shoulder Pain

Table 9 shows the cross-tabulation between the backpack weight group and shoulder pain. The Pearson Chi-Square test (C) in Table 10 produced a significant result, $\chi^2 (2, N = 96) = 28.32, p < .001$, indicating a strong and statistically significant association between backpack weight and the presence of shoulder pain. Notably, students carrying heavier backpacks were far more likely to experience shoulder pain compared to those with lighter loads.

Table 9. Bag Weight Group and Shoulder Pain Cross tabulation

			ShoulderPain		Total
			No	Yes	
BagWeightGroup	Light	Count	29	1	30
		Expected Count	25.0	5.0	30.0
	Medium	Count	49	8	57
		Expected Count	47.5	9.5	57.0
	Heavy	Count	2	7	9
		Expected Count	7.5	1.5	9.0
Total		Count	80	16	96
		Expected Count	80.0	16.0	96.0

Table 10. Chi-square Test (C)

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	28.324	2	.000
Likelihood Ratio	21.966	2	.000

CONCLUSION

The study investigated the effect of backpack use on the spinal health of lower-level high school students. The findings revealed significant relationships between backpack weight and self-reported shoulder and back pain, with heavier backpacks being associated with a higher prevalence of discomfort. Also, bag weight significantly influences spinal length, with heavier backpacks associated with greater reductions. While most students reported no back or shoulder pain, a notable minority did, highlighting the potential health risks of carrying heavy backpacks. In light of these findings, the study recommends implementing ergonomic measures, such as implementing locker systems in schools, educating students on how to use backpacks properly, and enforcing rules that restrict backpack weight. Future research should explore the long-term implications of excessive backpack use, including its impact on spinal development, and assess the effectiveness of interventions designed to mitigate these risks.

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CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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APPENDIX

Table 1. Information on All Subjects Captured in the Study

S/N	Sex	Age	Weight	Bag Weight	SPLM (cm)	Height M (cm)	SPLA (cm)	Height A (cm)	Shoulder Pain	Back Pain	Bag Weight Group
1	M	11	29.0	7.5	14.0	155.0	15.1	145.0	Yes	No	Heavy
2	F	13	30.0	6.0	13.5	155.0	12.7	163.5	Yes	No	Medium
3	F	13	38.0	5.0	13.2	161.0	14.3	151.5	Yes	No	Medium
4	M	13	51.0	5.5	15.0	155.0	13.5	160.0	Yes	No	Medium
5	F	13	44.0	5.8	15.0	155.0	13.5	152.5	Yes	No	Medium
6	F	12	42.0	5.6	14.7	163.0	15.5	164.5	Yes	No	Medium
7	M	12	44.5	4.5	15.0	165.0	17.0	164.5	No	No	Medium
8	F	12	46.5	6.5	13.5	158.0	15.0	157.5	Yes	Yes	Heavy
9	F	13	54.0	5.0	16.5	155.0	15.7	155.6	No	No	Medium
10	F	14	44.0	9.0	15.0	161.0	15.3	162.0	Yes	Yes	Heavy
11	F	13	39.0	6.0	15.5	152.0	14.4	163.3	No	No	Medium
12	M	13	30.5	4.9	12.5	143.0	12.2	160.5	No	No	Medium
13	F	14	41.0	2.5	13.5	156.0	15.0	158.2	No	No	Light
14	F	14	42.5	5.0	14.2	162.0	15.5	162.5	No	No	Medium
15	M	13	45.5	4.0	15.6	164.0	16.5	166.0	No	No	Medium
16	M	15	34.0	4.5	14.2	152.0	15.0	154.0	No	No	Medium
17	M	12	35.5	4.5	13.7	153.0	15.6	152.5	No	No	Medium
18	M	12	34.0	4.5	14.6	151.0	16.2	149.5	No	No	Medium
19	M	13	30.0	4.5	12.5	147.0	12.3	163.5	No	No	Medium
20	M	12	44.5	9.0	13.8	162.5	10.0	162.5	Yes	Yes	Heavy
21	F	13	31.5	4.0	15.0	145.0	15.1	148.6	No	No	Medium
22	F	13	50.5	5.0	17.0	160.0	17.1	160.7	No	No	Medium
23	F	13	37.5	5.0	13.0	143.0	13.2	143.8	No	No	Medium
24	F	12	27.0	4.5	13.0	147.0	13.2	146.7	No	No	Medium
25	M	15	35.0	3.5	14.2	146.0	15.3	153.8	No	No	Medium
26	M	14	37.0	2.0	14.5	157.0	15.0	155.9	No	No	Light
27	M	12	34.5	3.5	14.5	145.0	14.2	148.0	No	No	Medium
28	M	12	23.5	3.0	15.0	138.5	14.3	145.0	No	No	Light
29	M	12	28.5	14.1	13.5	141.5	14.2	141.1	Yes	Yes	Heavy
30	M	13	55.5	0.5	14.5	156.0	15.6	155.5	No	No	Light
31	M	14	34.5	4.5	14.1	151.0	15.0	150.2	No	No	Medium

32	M	13	35.5	2.5	14.5	147.5	15.2	146.7	No	No	Light
33	F	13	39.5	9.5	15.0	158.0	16.0	158.0	Yes	Yes	Heavy
34	M	13	39.5	4.2	14.8	162.0	15.0	164.0	No	No	Medium
35	F	13	35.5	6.5	15.0	164.0	16.0	164.4	Yes	No	Heavy
36	F	13	31.5	3.5	14.0	152.7	14.1	151.5	No	No	Medium
37	F	13	33.0	6.5	14.8	154.0	16.0	158.8	No	No	Heavy
38	F	12	33.0	4.5	14.0	155.7	15.5	155.9	No	No	Medium
39	M	14	45.5	4.0	16.0	159.9	17.2	160.0	No	No	Medium
40	F	13	35.5	6.0	15.8	153.0	16.0	153.2	Yes	No	Medium
41	M	13	36.5	5.0	15.0	155.0	15.2	155.5	No	No	Medium
42	M	14	30.0	5.0	14.6	145.7	15.0	156.6	No	No	Medium
43	M	13	54.0	5.5	16.0	162.1	15.5	165.9	No	No	Medium
44	F	14	48.0	4.0	16.3	165.0	16.2	167.9	No	No	Medium
45	M	14	37.0	4.0	15.0	157.0	15.2	152.4	No	No	Medium
46	M	13	30.0	5.5	14.1	153.4	14.0	155.7	Yes	No	Medium
47	F	13	40.0	2.5	14.5	154.8	14.8	154.4	No	No	Light
48	M	14	29.5	4.0	14.5	143.6	15.0	142.6	No	No	Medium
49	F	15	47.0	4.0	16.2	174.6	17.2	175.7	No	No	Medium
50	F	13	36.5	5.0	14.9	154.2	15.2	162.2	No	No	Medium
51	F	15	51.0	5.0	16.0	170.8	16.5	170.9	No	No	Medium
52	F	12	27.5	4.0	13.2	143.5	14.0	145.2	No	No	Medium
53	F	14	37.5	5.0	14.5	152.9	15.5	162.1	No	No	Medium
54	F	13	41.5	5.0	13.5	154.0	15.2	155.5	No	No	Medium
55	F	14	40.0	3.0	14.1	153.0	14.0	151.1	No	No	Light
56	F	14	38.9	5.5	13.7	150.0	13.6	148.0	No	No	Medium
57	F	12	51.0	5.5	14.0	149.9	16.0	148.9	No	No	Medium
58	F	14	43.0	3.0	14.7	151.0	15.5	150.5	No	No	Light
59	F	13	52.0	5.0	16.5	163.3	17.3	162.4	No	No	Medium
60	F	14	33.0	5.5	13.5	148.8	13.8	148.8	No	No	Medium
61	F	14	47.0	6.0	18.1	173.7	18.2	173.2	No	No	Medium
62	M	11	31.0	1.5	14.0	143.6	15.0	143.4	No	No	Light
63	F	13	27.0	44.5	12.1	140.2	13.2	138.9	No	No	Heavy
64	M	12	27.5	4.0	14.1	142.9	14.5	143.4	No	No	Medium
65	M	12	34.0	2.0	14.1	148.3	15.0	148.0	No	No	Light
66	M	12	30.5	3.4	14.4	142.5	14.5	143.5	No	No	Medium
67	M	13	35.6	2.0	14.1	153.9	14.5	153.3	No	No	Light
68	F	13	45.5	3.5	15.0	154.4	16.0	155.7	No	No	Medium
69	M	13	22.4	2.1	13.0	155.0	13.5	144.4	No	No	Light
70	M	13	30.0	2.5	13.3	148.0	14.6	144.0	No	No	Light
71	M	13	30.0	3.4	13.0	140.9	13.7	140.3	No	No	Medium
72	M	13	42.0	1.5	14.0	157.7	14.3	158.7	No	No	Light
73	M	12	28.0	2.0	15.0	144.5	15.2	144.8	No	No	Light

74	M	13	46.9	4.0	15.5	160.5	15.7	158.0	No	No	Medium
75	F	12	33.5	1.5	13.7	142.5	14.0	142.2	No	No	Light
76	M	15	54.5	3.8	15.0	157.6	16.6	156.0	No	No	Medium
77	F	12	29.0	2.0	14.2	145.0	15.1	144.6	Yes	Yes	Light
78	F	14	35.5	4.5	16.2	152.2	16.1	153.0	No	No	Medium
79	M	13	39.0	1.5	16.3	158.0	15.2	157.2	No	No	Light
80	M	11	25.0	2.0	14.7	140.5	15.5	142.0	No	No	Light
81	M	14	36.5	2.0	15.3	145.6	16.0	152.9	No	No	Light
82	M	13	31.0	2.5	13.2	142.2	14.0	142.3	No	No	Light
83	M	14	41.0	1.5	15.0	159.4	15.2	158.9	No	No	Light
84	M	10	23.5	3.2	12.7	136.4	13.5	135.9	No	No	Medium
85	M	11	28.0	2.5	13.0	136.0	13.2	137.7	No	No	Light
86	M	12	27.0	2.5	12.5	133.2	13.5	132.9	No	No	Light
87	M	10	30.5	2.2	13.5	143.0	14.2	141.3	No	No	Light
88	F	11	45.0	2.9	14.5	146.0	15.0	146.3	No	No	Light
89	M	14	29.5	2.9	14.2	144.5	14.0	144.2	No	No	Light
90	F	11	33.5	4.5	13.2	145.9	14.0	145.6	No	No	Medium
91	M	12	33.5	5.0	12.5	143.5	14.0	143.6	No	No	Medium
92	M	10	31.5	3.0	13.1	145.0	14.2	145.6	No	No	Light
93	M	9	29.0	3.0	13.1	133.1	13.5	132.7	No	No	Light
94	F	10	29.0	2.9	13.0	140.5	14.5	138.9	No	No	Light
95	M	10	28.0	3.5	14.6	145.8	15.6	145.2	No	No	Medium
96	F	11	29.5	6.0	12.2	145.8	13.3	145.4	Yes	No	Medium

